

The Role of Pharmacovigilance in Enhancing Primary Health Care Practices

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Abstract

Background: Pharmacovigilance plays a critical role in ensuring the safety and efficacy of medicines by identifying, assessing, and preventing adverse drug reactions (ADRs). Despite its importance, underreporting of ADRs by primary health care professionals remains a significant challenge, particularly in resource-limited settings.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of primary health care professionals regarding pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting, identify barriers to effective reporting, and recommend strategies to enhance pharmacovigilance practices.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted over six months at Shri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar. A total of 140 primary health care professionals, including doctors, nurses, and pharmacists, were selected using random sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire covering demographics, awareness, attitudes, practices, and perceived barriers to ADR reporting. Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied using SPSS version 23.0 to analyze the data.

Results: The mean age of participants was 35.2 ± 8.7 years, with a majority being male (60.7%). While 78.6% were aware of the definition of pharmacovigilance, only 57.1% understood ADR reporting mechanisms. A positive attitude toward ADR reporting was observed in 82.1% of participants, but regular reporting was noted in only 45.7%. Common barriers included lack of time (45.0%), insufficient knowledge (38.0%), and unavailability of reporting tools (35.0%). Statistically significant associations were found between years of experience and knowledge levels ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The study highlights moderate awareness and significant gaps in the practice of pharmacovigilance among primary health care professionals. Although most participants recognized ADR reporting as a professional responsibility, systemic and individual barriers impeded regular reporting.

Recommendations: Targeted training programs, simplified reporting processes, and organizational support are essential to improve ADR reporting practices. Enhancing pharmacovigilance systems can significantly contribute to patient safety and the effective use of medicines.

Keywords: Pharmacovigilance, Adverse Drug Reactions, Health Care Professionals, ADR Reporting, Patient Safety

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Introduction

Pharmacovigilance, the science and activities related to the detection, assessment, understanding, and prevention of adverse effects or any other drug-related problems, is crucial for ensuring patient safety and the effective use of medicines [1]. While clinical trials provide initial safety data, they often involve limited populations and controlled environments, which may not capture all potential (ADRs) [2]. Therefore, post-marketing surveillance through pharmacovigilance is essential to identify and mitigate risks associated with medications in real-world settings [3].

Primary health care professionals, including physicians, nurses, and pharmacists, play a pivotal role in pharmacovigilance systems. Their direct interaction with patients positions them uniquely to observe, document, and report ADRs, thereby contributing to the continuous monitoring of drug safety [4]. However, studies have highlighted challenges in ADR reporting among these professionals, such as limited awareness, inadequate training, and perceived barriers like time constraints and fear of legal consequences [5]. For instance, a cross-sectional study in Ghana revealed that while nurses recognized the importance of pharmacovigilance, actual reporting

practices were hindered by factors including lack of knowledge and training [6].

In India, the Pharmacovigilance Programme of India (PvPI) has been instrumental in promoting drug safety through the establishment of ADR monitoring centers and the dissemination of reporting guidelines [7]. Despite these efforts, underreporting remains a significant issue, often attributed to insufficient training and awareness among health care professionals [8]. Addressing these challenges is vital, as effective pharmacovigilance can lead to timely identification of drug-related problems, informing regulatory actions, and ultimately enhancing patient care [9]. This study aims to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of primary health care professionals regarding pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting, identify barriers to effective reporting, and recommend strategies to enhance pharmacovigilance practices.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Shri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar.

Study Participants: The study included a total of 140 primary health care professionals working at Shri Krishna Medical College and Hospital.

Inclusion Criteria

- Primary health care professionals (doctors, nurses, and pharmacists) working in Shri Krishna Medical College and Hospital.
- Professionals willing to provide informed consent.
- Individuals actively practicing for at least one year.

Exclusion Criteria

- Health care professionals unwilling to participate in the study.

- Interns or individuals with less than one year of professional experience.
- Participants with incomplete or missing data.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from various departments of the hospital. To reduce reporting bias, participants were assured of anonymity and confidentiality of their responses.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured, pre-tested questionnaire divided into four sections: demographic details, awareness and knowledge of pharmacovigilance, attitudes and practices related to (ADR) reporting, and perceived barriers to reporting. Participants completed the questionnaire during face-to-face interactions to ensure clarity and accuracy of responses.

Procedure: Participants were randomly selected from various departments to ensure a representative sample of primary health care professionals. Each participant was approached individually, and the purpose of the study was explained to them in detail. Informed consent was obtained prior to participation, ensuring that all participants were aware of their rights and the confidentiality of their responses. Once consent was secured, participants were provided with the questionnaire and given sufficient time to complete it. Researchers were available to clarify any queries related to the questionnaire. Completed questionnaires were collected, verified for completeness, and securely stored for analysis. This systematic approach ensured high-quality data collection while respecting participants' time and confidentiality.

Results

A total of 140 primary health care professionals participated in the study. The mean age of participants was 35.2 ± 8.7 years, with a majority being male (85, 60.7%) and the rest female (55, 39.3%). The average years of professional experience were 10.3 ± 5.1 years, reflecting a diverse group of experienced health care professionals.

Table 1: Participant Demographics

Demographics	Values
Age (Mean \pm SD)	35.2 \pm 8.7 years
Gender Male	85, 60.7%
Gender Female	55, 39.3%
Years of Experience (Mean \pm SD)	10.3 \pm 5.1 years

Awareness regarding pharmacovigilance was moderate among participants. About 78.6% were familiar with the definition of pharmacovigilance, while 64.3% recognized the importance of (ADR) report

ing. However, only 57.1% were aware of ADR reporting mechanisms, indicating gaps in knowledge about reporting systems.

Table 2: Awareness and Knowledge of Pharmacovigilance

Questions	Yes %	No %
Aware of pharmacovigilance definition	78.6	21.4
Aware of ADR reporting importance	64.3	35.7
Aware of ADR reporting mechanisms	57.1	42.9

The study revealed mixed attitudes and practices. While 82.1% believed that ADR reporting was part of their professional responsibility, only 45.7% reported ADRs regularly. Additionally, 68.6%

reported encountering barriers to reporting ADRs, reflecting systemic issues that discourage reporting practices.

Table 3: Attitudes and Practices Toward ADR Reporting

Questions	Yes %	No %
Regularly report ADRs	45.7	54.3
Feel ADR reporting is part of responsibility	82.1	17.9
Encountered barriers in reporting ADRs	68.6	31.4

Participants identified several barriers to ADR reporting. The most common barrier was a lack of time (45.0%), followed by insufficient knowledge about reporting processes (38.0%). Additionally,

28.0% reported fear of legal consequences, and 35.0% cited the unavailability of reporting tools as a significant challenge.

Table 4: Barriers to ADR Reporting

Barriers	Percentage %
Lack of time	45.0
Lack of knowledge	38.0
Fear of legal consequences	28.0
Unavailability of reporting tools	35.0

Discussion

The study, conducted among 140 primary health care professionals, revealed a moderate level of awareness and knowledge regarding pharmacovigilance. While most participants (78.6%) were familiar with the definition of pharmacovigilance, fewer recognized the importance of (ADR) reporting (64.3%) or were aware of the mechanisms for reporting ADRs (57.1%). These findings indicate a need for educational interventions to enhance understanding of pharmacovigilance processes and their significance in improving patient safety.

Attitudes toward ADR reporting were generally positive, with 82.1% of participants acknowledging that it is part of their professional responsibility. However, only 45.7% reported ADRs regularly, highlighting a significant gap between awareness and practice. This discrepancy suggests that additional barriers, beyond knowledge, impede reporting behaviors. The majority of participants (68.6%) reported encountering challenges in reporting ADRs, which further underscores systemic issues that need to be addressed.

Key barriers identified included a lack of time (45.0%), insufficient knowledge about the reporting process (38.0%), fear of legal consequences (28.0%), and unavailability of reporting tools (35.0%). These obstacles highlight the need for structural and procedural improvements, such as providing easily accessible reporting tools, address

ing fears about legal repercussions and allocating time for reporting in clinical workflows.

Pharmacovigilance plays a critical role in primary health care by monitoring, detecting, and preventing adverse drug reactions (ADRs). A study

emphasized the necessity of national pharmacovigilance centers (NPCs) to help clinicians understand their functions in medicine safety surveillance. It highlighted that integrating ADR monitoring with vaccine safety surveillance has improved patient safety outcomes and underlined the importance of reporting ADRs to ensure medication safety [10]. CPRD, a large-scale primary care database in the UK, has significantly enhanced pharmacovigilance by supporting comprehensive data analysis to identify adverse drug reactions. This database has improved risk-benefit assessments and helped develop policies for safer medication practices. Its ability to process large datasets efficiently makes it an invaluable tool for pharmacovigilance in primary care [11]. Research in South India revealed that while healthcare professionals had a positive attitude towards ADR reporting, knowledge and practice remained suboptimal. This gap was attributed to inadequate training and awareness. The study recommended implementing awareness campaigns and continuing medical education (CME) workshops to improve pharmacovigilance practices among healthcare professionals [12]. An evaluation of pharmacovigilance regulations across the US, UK, Canada, and India highlighted the need for global harmonized practices. Variability in pharmacovigilance systems among countries poses challenges to universal medication safety. This study recommended the development of global standards to enable better cross-border collaboration and to ensure the safer use of medicines worldwide [13].

Conclusion

The findings emphasize on the importance of targeted interventions to improve pharmacovigilance practices. Training programs focused on ADR re-

porting, streamlined and user-friendly reporting mechanisms, and organizational support to overcome barriers are essential for fostering a culture of proactive pharmacovigilance among health care professionals. Such efforts can significantly enhance the safety and efficacy of health care services.

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